

Attract attention on your resource

Constantly working on the visibility of your resource is essential to position it as a reference in your domain.

Get listed

Getting your resource added to **prestigious lists** curated by **international organizations** will increase **visibility** and **recognition**.

Consider applying for:

- 🔗 **SIB/ELIXIR-CH Service Delivery Plan (SDP)** identifies resources that provide long-term, sustainable, and high-quality services to the bioinformatics community.
- 🔗 **SIB Resources** form a portfolio of carefully selected databases and software tools from among SIB groups identified by SIB's Scientific Advisory Board.
- 🔗 **ELIXIR [Core Data Resources \(CDR\)](#) and [Deposition Databases \(EDD\)](#)** are a set of European data resources of fundamental importance to the wider life-science community and the long term preservation of biological data.
- 🔗 **ELIXIR [Recommended Interoperability Resources \(RIRs\)](#)** facilitate the FAIR-supporting activities in scientific research.
- 🔗 **[Global Core Biodata Resources \(GCBRs\)](#)** are of fundamental importance to the global life sciences community and the long-term preservation of biological data.

Contact the Biodata Resources team for more information.

Be visible at congresses and meetings

- 🔗 Plan the number of congresses and meetings to attend with your teammates each year.
- 🔗 Be easily **recognizable**, wear branded pins or T-shirts.
- 🔗 Bring goodies (like stickers or else) to engage attendees.
- 🔗 Use the **SIB booth**, if available, for networking.
- 🔗 Contact the **Communications team** to **promote** your attendance on **social media**.

Use the opportunities provided by your SIB membership

Participate in the initiatives to catch the limelight, such as:

- 🔗 **SIB Remarkable Outputs**
Annual competition.
- 🔗 **Bioinformatics Awards**
Bi-annual competition (organized by SIB).
- 🔗 **SIB days / [BC]? participation** in the scientific committee, talks & posters, social activities...
- 🔗 **Focus groups**
Participate or launch your own topic (see [existing topics](#)) & look for partnerships.

Getting featured thanks to these initiatives guarantees that your resource will also get visibility in dedicated **SIB social media** campaigns and **website**.

Keep the Communication team in the loop

When your team is represented at a conference, panel, or in the media, inform the Communications team in advance.

They will help you promote it in the most efficient way.

Propose and prepare training kits to reach students

Getting students hooked on your resource early helps to ensure they will use it **throughout their career**.

Reach out to university biology and/or bioinformatics departments to propose a training kit or even an intervention in courses to show **how to use the resource** and for which purposes.

Share impact stories on your website and elsewhere

Impact stories highlight how your resource drives **innovation** in life sciences, helping **potential users** see its practical applications and giving **decision-makers** a clear sense of its importance.

SIB features these stories on its [website](#), **social media**, and different **reports**. Do not hesitate to contact the Communications team for assistance.

Ask your users for testimonials or referrals

- Ask your users for **testimonials** and **referrals** on their social media or website.
- Request **quotes** from Scientific Advisory Board members to **share** on your platforms or through SIB communications.

Get involved in societies

Such as the [International Society for Computational Biology \(ISCB\)](#), [Life Science Switzerland \(LS²\)](#) or any other one related to your user base.

Develop your social media presence

Regular updates on relevant social channels **build trust** and strengthen **relationships with users**. SIB currently focuses on **LinkedIn** and **Mastodon** for institutional communications. Contact the **Communications team** for platform expertise and a **tailored strategy**.

- **LinkedIn showcase page:** the communications team encourages the creation of LinkedIn Showcase pages to publish updates independently but with full support from the communications team. The first example is the [Cellosaurus showcase page](#).

Your contacts:

[Communications team](#)
[Biodata Resources team](#)

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics

